

INTEGRATION OF UZBEKISTAN INTO GLOBAL MARKETS: FACTORS OF INCREASING EXPORT AUTHORITY AND COMPETITIVENESS

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the factors of improving export potential and competitiveness in the process of Uzbekistan's integration into world markets. Although the share of raw materials in the country's exports remains high in recent years, significant measures are being taken to expand the share of finished products, services and high value-added goods. The study analyzes international experience, statistical indicators and institutional reforms, identifies priority areas for expanding export markets, increasing product diversity and forming competitive advantages. Finally, practical recommendations are developed for Uzbekistan's deeper integration into global value chains and effective implementation of its export strategy.*

Keywords: *export, WTO, competitiveness, diversification, international experience, economic stability.*

Uzbekistan has been making rapid strides in recent years, accelerating economic reforms and aiming for deep integration into the international trading system. The country's foreign trade policy has prioritized export diversification, expanding the production of high-value-added products, and ensuring international competitiveness. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-158[1] dated September 11, 2023 “On the Strategy “Uzbekistan-2030” [1] focuses on increasing the country's export potential in the coming years. The strategy consists of 100 goals, and goal 55 is set as “Strengthening the export potential of the national economy and sharply increasing the share of products with high added value in its structure.” This goal includes tasks such as doubling export volumes to \$45 billion, increasing the number of enterprises operating on the basis of international standards by 10 times, and establishing special economic zones with 50 prestigious world brands. Goal 93 of this strategy is also a multi-year priority plan for our state. Uzbekistan's full membership in the World Trade Organization (WTO) will not only open new market doors for the country, but also encourage local manufacturers to create competitive products. Adaptation to WTO norms will improve national exports in terms of quality and certification requirements, which will allow for deeper integration into global value chains. Therefore, expanding the export structure and increasing competitiveness are crucial for the country's economic stability and gaining a strong position in world markets.

In recent years, Uzbekistan's exports have shown a steady growth trend. However, the goal is to double the volume of exports. According to the National Statistics Committee, exports are growing at a good rate (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of Uzbekistan's export volume in 2020-2024.[2]

According to the data in the diagram, Uzbekistan's export volume shows a steady growth trend in 2020-2024. Exports, which amounted to 15.1 billion US dollars in 2020, increased by 10% to 16.6 billion US dollars in 2021. In 2022, this figure amounted to 19.7 billion US dollars, an increase of almost 18% per year. In 2023, export volumes increased significantly and reached 24.9 billion US dollars, an increase of 26%. The forecast value for 2024 is 26.9 billion US dollars, which is an increase of almost 78% compared to 2020. Such a positive picture of the dynamics indicates the expansion of production capacities in the national economy, diversification of the export structure, and the acceleration of integration processes into world markets[3].

One of the main priorities of Uzbekistan's foreign trade policy is export diversification. Along with the stable growth of export volumes in recent years, the share of raw materials in its composition remains high. In particular, resources such as gold, gas, and cotton fiber make up a significant part of exports. This creates a high level of dependence on price fluctuations in foreign markets. In this situation, as stipulated in the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, expanding the export of finished products with high added value, mechanical engineering, chemical and pharmaceutical industries, electrical engineering, and food industry products is of crucial importance. In particular, in 2022–2023, a significant increase was observed in exports of textiles, non-ferrous metal products, and the automotive industry, which indicates the beginning of the process of structural changes. Therefore, when expanding exports, it is necessary not only to expand the product range, but also to diversify geographically - to develop new regional markets. Also, the process of Uzbekistan's accession to the WTO can accelerate the diversification of the export structure. Because this process strengthens the requirements for international certification, increases competitiveness and opens new market doors. Thus, along with quantitative growth, qualitative diversification ensures the sustainable economic development of the country.

Uzbekistan's deep integration into the world economic system sets new strategic goals for the country. One of the most important of these is to increase the competitiveness of the national

economy. The main factors determining competitiveness are production efficiency, the pace of technological innovation, the development of the transport and logistics system, and the simplification of the regulatory framework. Consistent measures taken in recent years in these areas are expanding the openness of the economy and opportunities for accessing foreign markets. The figures clearly confirm this: during 2020-2024, the country's export volume increased from 15.1 billion US dollars to 26.9 billion dollars. Such a growth in exports demonstrates the practical effectiveness of steps taken to improve structural reforms, increase production efficiency, and liberalize foreign trade mechanisms.

The process of full membership in the World Trade Organization (WTO) represents a qualitatively new stage for Uzbekistan. Because WTO membership expands the opportunities of national exporters in the international arena and encourages them to operate in accordance with global standards. This requires, first of all, passing international certification processes, adapting to technical regulations and quality standards, introducing innovative technologies, and expanding the product range. Thus, joining the WTO will not only strengthen Uzbekistan's position in the world market, but also serve to increase the share of high-value-added products in the export structure. As a result, a national economy will be formed that is ready for international competition, diversified, and capable of sustainable growth. This process will give a strong impetus to the acceleration of economic modernization, the expansion of foreign trade relations, and the strengthening of the country's position in the global economic system in the long term.

As Uzbekistan's export policy aligns with WTO integration and increasing the competitiveness of its national economy, the experience of advanced countries provides important lessons. In particular, Germany's export policy relies on high-value-added industrial products. In 2023, mechanical engineering products accounted for 17 percent of the country's exports, a result that is closely linked to a strategic focus on innovative research and development (R&D) programs. The experience of Denmark is also of particular importance. This country has strengthened its competitiveness by taking leading positions in the export of green technologies and introducing energy-efficient production and renewable energy solutions to international markets. Thus, it can be seen that the export of environmentally friendly technologies provides not only economic, but also social stability. Referring to the experience of the Asian region, South Korea radically strengthened its quality control and certification system during its WTO accession process. As a result, rapid growth was observed in the export of electronics, automotive, and high-tech products. Kazakhstan, after joining the WTO in 2015, has significantly increased its export volume by expanding its foreign trade flows and modernizing its logistics infrastructure. These experiences show that the production of high-value-added products, improving the quality and certification system, and increasing logistics efficiency are also strategic priorities for Uzbekistan. Statistical data also confirm this: in 2020-2024, the country's export volume increased by \$11.8 billion, reaching \$26.9 billion. These results clearly demonstrate the correctness of the chosen strategy and the practical effectiveness of the reforms initiated.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan has achieved significant results in recent years in steadily increasing export volumes, diversifying their composition, and expanding the share of high-value-added products. The increase in export volumes from \$15.1 billion to \$26.9 billion in 2020–2024 indicates that the country's economic policy is on the right track. Full accession to the WTO is expected to take this process to a new level and further strengthen Uzbekistan's

position in the international trading system. On this basis, the following proposals can be put forward:

1. Expanding the share of innovative products - encouraging the production and export of technological and industrial products with high added value.

2. Developing a quality and certification system - increasing the competitiveness of exporters through the widespread introduction of international standards that comply with WTO requirements.

3. Financial support for exports - facilitating the access of small and medium-sized businesses to foreign markets by expanding export credit agencies and insurance mechanisms.

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